

Clinical Research Center Administrator Carmen Rosas Lukovich (she/her)

"If researchers and coordinators tell me that a study or clinical trial went more smoothly because of the center's resources, then I know I'm doing my job."

Bio

Carmen became Administrator of the clinical research center after a career in clinical drug trials. The center offers the support staff, equipment, and resources to help investigators conduct clinical studies and trials. Provided resources include various labs, a pharmacy, and support with informatics, protocol development, biospecimen collection, specimen processing, and REDCap. The center also provides assistance with grants, subcontracts, new funding streams such as crowdsourcing, and protection of intellectual property. Carmen employs experience and strategic partnerships to identify trends and needs for the center, and to plan accordingly for the center's direction and financial needs. She is establishing metrics to assess the center's operation and services.

Management of the center's budget, strategic planning, personnel, and fundraising are all parts of Carmen's work, through which she employs skills in analysis, negotiation, and teambuilding. Carmen employs full knowledge of clinical operations and institutional resources to serve the clinical and research needs of the center. Carmen skillfully balances a strategic outlook with a boots-on-the-ground commitment to her center's staff and their well-being.

Education: MS, Chemistry; PhD, Biochemistry

Years of experience: 12

Work location: Frequent remote work on her laptop

Goals

- Establish productive partnerships at leadership level with the local finance and informatics offices
- Expand the program of investigator training to include research methods and scientific writing
- Include the community in PI training to encourage better grasp of health disparities
- Cultivate continuous process improvement

Software attitude & use

- Relies on research administrators and the sponsored research office for reports from financial and budgeting software programs
- Carmen organized the center's website design with employee and front-end developer help
- General: Microsoft Office Suite
- Collaboration: Box, Zoom
- Specialized resources: grant management platforms and regulatory and funder websites. She wishes these sites were easier to navigate, often delegating information retrieval to her assistant

Outputs

- Collaborates on conference presentations with her colleagues
- Speeches to funding organizations
- Writes and reviews grants

Pain Points

- Needs institutional funds to sustain the clinical research center
- Constant pressure to monitor the fundraising landscape
- Misconceptions about center's remit

Motivators

- Optimize clinical research by allowing more trials to be completed with more consented participants, and with quicker initiation times
- Facilitate compliance and training that will protect human subjects from harm caused by bad research practice
- Save her organization time and money by retaining a talented research staff pool

Wants/Needs

- To develop and implement metrics (or have the CTSA Program provide them) that measure study management improvements through process efficiencies
- A digital solution to inform researchers about resources available at their institution, such as a web portal encompassing trials and recruitment information, knowledge bases, data management tools, etc.
- To update support staff job descriptions based on a combination of training, skills, and competencies

Professional Development

Carmen ensures the center offers trainings in research methods, grants, scientific writing, proposal development, epidemiology, leadership, community-based research, cultural humility, and use of national public datasets

To improve the center's processes, Carmen wants to survey the PIs and support staff about their needs, but lacks the expertise to write the survey herself as well as funds to hire a professional evaluator